

ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF STEARIC ACID HYDROSOL. PART II.

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The solubility of stearic acid at 35° and at 50° is $1.17 \times 10^{-5}N$ and $5.77 \times 10^{-6}N$ respectively. The dissociation constant of the acid has been found to be 1.7×10^{-6} at 35° and 2.6×10^{-6} at 50°. The p_H of the sol at 50° has been found to be less than that at 35° but the total acidity as is to be expected in the case in which the whole acid reacts, remains the same at 50°. The hydrogen ion activity of the sol increases on the addition of neutral salts. The solubility of barium and calcium stearates at 35° has been found to be $9.02 \times 10^{-6}N$ and $6.15 \times 10^{-6}N$ and at 50° $2.21 \times 10^{-6}N$ and $2.33 \times 10^{-5}N$ respectively.

In Part I of this series (*This issue* p. 563) electrometric titrations of stearic acid sols with bases NaOH, NH₄OH, Ba(OH)₂ and Ca(OH)₂ have been reported and it has been shown that the titration curves, though to some extent resemble those of a weak acid in true solution, are different and that the total acidity as obtained by titration agrees fairly well with the stoichiometric concentration of the acid as obtained by extraction. Neutralisable acids in presence of neutral salts like KCl, BaCl₂, CaCl₂ has been shown to be the same as that of the pure sol. An explanation has been offered from the phase rule considering the sol as a two phase system.

This paper deals with (i) the dissociation constant and solubility of the acid, (ii) the p_H change on the addition of neutral and hydrolysable salts and the solubility of calcium and barium stearates, and (iii) the effect of temperature on p_H , dissociation constant and solubility of the acid, nature of the titration curves with bases and neutral salts and the solubility of barium and calcium stearates.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangements were the same as described in Part I of this paper. Sols were prepared from stearic acid obtained by twice crystallising Merck's extra pure stearic acid from absolute alcohol and conductivity water. For conductivity determinations a cell of the Washburn type containing unplatinised electrodes was used. The electrodes were large and were very close to each other. The capacity of the cell was 50 c.c. and the cell constant 0.01. A 1000 cycle Vreeland oscillator was employed as the source of the alternating current and a Leeds and Northrup

roller conductivity bridge was used. A water thermostat was used at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$ and at $50 \pm 0.05^{\circ}$.

Dissociation Constant and Solubility of the Acid.

The titration curves of stearic acid sols with NaOH though to some extent resemble those of a weak acid with a strong base are different. The Henderson equation cannot therefore be applied to determine the dissociation constant of the acid from the potentiometric titration curves.

Taking colloidal stearic acid to behave as a weak acid obeying the law of mass action, and assuming the activity coefficient to be unity at these low concentrations, the following equation should hold :

$$[H^+][\text{Stearate}^-] = K[\text{H-Stearate}] = K.S_u = S$$

where S_u is the concentration of the undissociated acid in equilibrium with the solid phase. For the pure sol $[H^+] = [\text{Stearate}^-]$ and $[H^+]$ can be obtained from (i) the p_H of the sol, (ii) specific conductivity of the sol to which $[H^+]$ is related by the equation :

$$(u + v). [H^+] \times 10^3 = \rho \text{ (specific conductivity in rec. ohms).}$$

Further, in the case of the titration of the sol with NaOH, the above equation reduces to

$$[H^+][\text{Stearate}^-] = [H^+]\{[Na^+] + [H^+] - [OH^-]\} = K.S_u$$

since $[\text{Stearate}^-] = [Na^+] + [H^+] - [OH^-]$ and therefore, the $K.S_u$ can be evaluated from definite points in the titration curves, $[Na^+]$ being known from the amount of alkali added to the sol and $[H^+]$ and $[OH^-]$ from the p_H of the sol at that point. The results obtained by different methods are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Sol.	(a) p_H of sol.	(b) $K.S_u \times 10^{-12}$ Sp. condty.	(c) Points in the curves.			
			$\frac{1}{4}$.	$\frac{1}{2}$.	$\frac{3}{4}$.	final.
A	17.3	21.00	19.0	20.20	26.10	25.70
B	19.05	25.90	26.0	24.70		
C	29.89	24.90	—	—	19.60	18.4

It is interesting to note that the values obtained by different methods are of the same order and do not differ much from one another considering the experimental difficulties. Now the values calculated from the p_H of the sol are expected to be in larger error. The values obtained from $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{3}{4}$ and final neutralisation points of NaOH titration curves are liable to be in error also because the slopes of the curves at these points are considerable.

The values from specific conductivity data and from the half neutralisation point are less liable to error and the mean of these values is 21×10^{-12} .

FIG. 1.

Sol A.

In order to evaluate therefore the dissociation constant of the acid, S_u , the concentration of the undissociated acid in equilibrium with the solid phase must be known. Stearic acid is a weak acid and further is present mostly in the solid insoluble state and under these conditions therefore S_u can be taken to be equal to the solubility of the acid without any serious error. The solubility of stearic acid as obtained by various workers are widely divergent and are reproduced below for comparison in Table II.

TABLE II.

Author.	Reference.	Solubility.
Moore, Hutchinson and Wilson	<i>Biochem. J.</i> , 1909, 12, 347.	$3.5 \times 10^{-3}N$ at 37° .
Siedell	Bull. No. 67, <i>Hygienic Laboratory U. S. Public Health Service.</i>	$1.2 \times 10^{-4}N$ at 25° .
McBain & Peaker	<i>Pro. Roy. Soc.</i> , 1929, A, 125,	$4.1 \times 10^{-7}N$ at 25° .

It was therefore thought desirable to determine the solubility of the acid. Large quantities of stearic acid hydrosol and also conductivity water saturated with stearic acid by shaking or by keeping at $60-65^\circ$ for several hours and then cooling to the desired temperature, were ultrafiltered through 'Cella' finest membrane. The filtrate was evaporated and weighed from a platinum bowl in small instalments. The results obtained are given below in Table III.

TABLE III.

No. of expts.	Solubility of the acid.	No. of expts.	Solubility of the acid.
1	$1.05 \times 10^{-5}N$	3	$1.19 \times 10^{-5}N$
2	1.16	4	1.18

On dividing the mean value of $K.S_u$ by the mean value of the solubility, the dissociation constant of stearic acid becomes 1.77×10^{-6} at 35° . The value obtained as a second approximation from $[H^+]$ calculated from the solubility and dissociation constant thus obtained is 1.3×10^{-6} .

FIG. 2.

Sol C.

Interactions with Neutral and Hydrolysable Salts.

(a) *Interactions with Neutral Salts - p_H change.*—On the addition of KCl, BaCl₂ and CaCl₂, the p_H diminishes (Fig. 1, curves 1, 2, 3, 4; Fig. 2, curves 5, 6, 7; Fig. 4, curves 14 and 15). Compared to the bivalent cations calcium and barium, potassium has a relatively smaller effect. BaCl₂ produces a steeper initial drop in p_H but at higher concentration CaCl₂ appears to be relatively more effective. This observation is similar to that reported by Mukherjee, Mitra and Mukherjee (*Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 1, No. 10, p. 227), in the case of silicic acid and hydrogen clay sols where the difference has been attributed to the greater coagulating effect of BaCl₂.

The liberation of hydrogen ions on the addition of neutral salts is the result of the formation of either (i) the corresponding stearate in the solid state or (ii) undissociated salt molecules, adhering possibly by lattice forces to the surface of the particles of the acid. The barium or calcium salts being less soluble than the potassium salts, BaCl₂ or CaCl₂ have greater power for lowering the p_H . The analysis of the ultrafiltrate shows that the reaction that takes place is, however, far from being complete, only a relatively small proportion of stearic acid reacts with the salt and that HCl is produced by the reaction :

If solid stearates are formed the following reactions are expected at constant temperature and pressure:

$[\text{H}^+][\text{Stearate}^-] = S$, $[\text{K}^+][\text{Stearate}^-] = S_1$, $[\text{Ba}^{++}][\text{Stearate}^-]^2 = S_2$ and $[\text{Ca}^{++}][\text{Stearate}^-]^2 = S_3$ where S , S_1 , S_2 and S_3 represent the ionic products of stearic acid, potassium stearate, barium stearate and calcium stearate respectively.

Therefore, $[\text{K}^+]/[\text{H}^+] = S_1/S = Z_1$,

$$\sqrt{[\text{Ba}^{++}]/[\text{H}^+]} = \sqrt{S_2/S} = Z_2,$$

and

$$\sqrt{[\text{Ca}^{++}]/[\text{H}^+]} = \sqrt{S_3/S} = Z_3.$$

The calculated hydrogen ion concentrations are liable to a greater error than the p_H values. The concentration of barium ions have been obtained by subtracting half of the increase of the concentration of hydrogen ions from the molar concentration of barium chloride added to the sol.

Values of these ratios calculated from curves 1 and 3 are plotted in curves 1' and 3' in Fig. 1 and from curves 5, 6 and 7 in curves 5' 6' and 7'

in Fig. 2. For BaCl_2 and CaCl_2 , the 'Z' values after an initial variation tend to become constant, showing that solid calcium and barium stearates are formed. For KCl, however, the ratio varies continuously with the concentration of the salt. The latter probably forms an acid stearate or normal stearate which does not form a separate phase but is stable at a certain p_{H} .

It also appears from the 'Z' curves that complete equilibrium between the solid phases and the solution is difficult of attainment during the titration. From the 'Z' values the solubilities of barium and calcium stearates can be calculated. As already put forward

$$Z = \frac{\sqrt{S_2}}{S} = \frac{\sqrt{[\text{Ba}^{++}]}}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

and since S and Z are known the value of S_2 , the ionic product of barium stearate and thence the solubility of barium stearate can be calculated. The solubility thus obtained from different Z values are given in Table IV.

In a similar way the solubility of calcium stearate has been found out (Table IV, columns 4 and 5).

TABLE IV.

Sol.	Z values.	Solubility of Ba-stearate at 35°.	Z values.	Solubility of Ca-stearate at 35°.
A	2.63×10^3	$9.12 \times 10^{-6}N$	1.57×10^3	$6.45 \times 10^{-6}N$
	2.61	9.08	1.42	6.05
	2.45	8.7	1.51	6.3
C	2.5	8.83	1.5	6.28
	2.63	9.12	1.4	6.02
	2.74	9.3	1.34	5.83

(b) *Interactions with Hydrolysable Salts.*—A distinction between exchange and hydrolytic acidities of soil developed on treating an acid soil with neutral and hydrolysable salts is usually made. Experiments with pure systems are likely to be helpful for a proper understanding of the theoretical basis of this distinction. Variations of H-ion activities of stearic acid sols on progressive additions of hydrolysable salts have been studied with this object in view.

FIG. 3.

Sol B.

FIG. 4.

Sol E.

Stearic acid sol C was titrated with sodium acetate, barium acetate and calcium acetate solutions. The salt solutions were in each case made neutral by the addition of the requisite amount of acetic acid before use.

The titration curves are shown in Fig. 3 (curves 8 and 9 with Na salt, 10 and 11 with Ba salts and 12 and 13 with Ca salts). With sodium acetate p_H increases continually and gradually approaches the p_H of the added neutral acetate. With barium and calcium acetates on the other hand the p_H at first passes through a maximum, then diminishes and finally increases slowly. The maxima and the middle of the diffuse minima occur at $5 \times 10^{-4}N$ and $3.45 \times 10^{-3}N$ respectively of both the added salts. The first value is somewhat less than the amount of the acid in the sol which is $6.5 \times 10^{-4}N$. The p_H at the maximum is 5.90-5.92 for Ba-acetate and 5.65 for calcium acetate. The curves are rather interesting. With increasing concentrations of barium and calcium ions insoluble stearates are formed and acetic acid is set free. This causes a lowering of the p_H , the rate of increase of free hydrogen ions falls off with the progress of the titration and the buffer action of the added salt, which has a higher p_H (7.0) becomes predominant. The p_H then rises slowly tending to approach the p_H of the acetate solution.

The Effect of Temperature on p_H , Dissociation Constant and Solubility of the Acid, Nature of the Titration Curves with Bases and Neutral Salts and the Solubility of Barium and Calcium Stearates.

The solubility of stearic acid increases with temperature. The solubility has been determined at 50° and has been found to be $5.77 \times 10^{-5} N$. In stearic acid sols the colloidal particles constitute the solid phase and the intermicellary liquid contains its saturated solution. The hydrogen ion concentration calculated from the solubility of the acid at 35° agrees fairly well with the observed hydrogen ion concentration of the sol; the observed hydrogen ion concentration for different sols and that calculated from the solubility are given in Table V.

TABLE V.

Sol.	Obs.	Calc. from solubility.
A	$3.9 \times 10^{-6} N$	$3.7 \times 10^{-6} N$
B	4.2	—
C	4.3	—
E	3.0	—

FIG. 5.

Sol D.

It appears therefore that the acid in solution is mainly responsible for the p_H of the solution. It is to be expected therefore that when with rise of temperature the solubility of the acid increases, the p_H of the sol should diminish. In order to verify this the p_H values of sols have been determined at 50° and it has been found that the p_H actually diminishes. The results obtained are given below in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Sol E	p_H of the sol	
	at 35° .	at 50°
Sol E	5.36	4.89
—	5.38	4.90
—	5.44	4.92

In stearic acid sols the whole of the acid reacts with the base and it is evident therefore that the total acidity of the sol should not change with rise of temperature. This is what has been experimentally found out (Fig. 5, curves 18, 19, 20, 21). The only difference that is observed is that the middle flat portion of the curve occurs at a lower p_H at higher temperatures.

The dissociation constant of the acid at 50° calculated from the hydrogen ion concentration of the sol at the temperature by the method already described gives the value, 2.8×10^{-6} .

TABLE VII.

Sol E.			
Z values of $BaCl_2$ titrations.	Solubility of Ba-stearate at 50° .	Z values of $CaCl_2$ titrations.	Solubility of Ca-stearate at 50° .
4.7×10^3	2.19×10^{-5}	5.08×3	2.29×10^{-5}
4.94	2.26	5.5	2.4
4.64	2.18	5.00	2.28

Stearic acid sol E has been titrated at 50° with neutral barium and calcium chlorides (Fig. 4, curves 16 and 17) and the 'Z' values calculated from these curves are given in Table VII. The solubility of calcium and barium stearates calculated from these 'Z' values are also given in Table VII.

In conclusion, I take this opportunity to offer my sincere thanks to Prof. J. N. Mukherjee, D.Sc., for his kind interest in the work. Thanks are also due to the University of Calcutta for awarding me a research scholarship during the tenure of which this work was done.

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